

FEATURES OF DIAGNOSING GASTROINTESTINAL ALLERGIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078302>

Keywords: Gastrointestinal allergy, allergic esophagitis, allergic gastritis, intestinal colic, allergic enteropathy, allergic colitis, malabsorption syndrome, ascites.

Introduction. The gastrointestinal system plays a key role in the complex mechanisms of immunoregulation. The common embryonic matrix of entodermic derivation of respiratory and gastrointestinal tissues confers immunological peculiarities regarding the early sensitization and activation of tolerance mechanisms to the digestive system. Usually, the antigens responsible of initial sensitization and thus of allergic reactions are subsequently well tolerated by complex mechanisms, including immunodeviation and immunotolerance. Such processes initiate during fetal life, when allergens and immunoglobulins in their Fab component are ingested by the fetus by swallowing amniotic liquid, and contact with the primordial gastrointestinal immune system activates the antigen-presenting cells (APC) already present in some mucosal intestinal sites

The clinical manifestations of this pathology depend on the level of damage to the gastrointestinal tract and may manifest as nausea, vomiting, abdominal pain, diarrhea, intestinal obstruction, malabsorption syndrome, ascites, weight loss. The following types of gastrointestinal allergies are distinguished: allergic esophagitis; allergic gastritis; intestinal colic; allergic enteropathy; allergic colitis; signs of cheilitis, gingivitis, glossitis: swelling of the lips, oral mucosa, tongue; recurrent aphthous stomatitis.

Methods: 1. Collection of allergy history - hereditary history of allergies; the child has skin or respiratory allergies. 2. Determination of clinical features: connection of the disease with food allergens; abdominal pain, intestinal colic; dyspeptic symptoms (vomiting, loose stools with clear mucus and blood); normal body temperature, no intoxication; positive dynamics after eliminating the allergen and prescribing antihistamines. 3. Laboratory research methods include: general blood test - eosinophilia; coprogram - light mucus and red blood cells in the stool; endoscopy: esophagus, stomach, duodenum - pale mucous membrane, mucus, semolina symptom, linear grooves; histology ≥ 20 eosinophils per field of view. 4. Specific allergological examination: determination of total IgE; determination of allergen-specific IgE and IgG4.

Results: Using these diagnostic methods, we can make an accurate diagnosis in a timely manner and begin the necessary treatment sooner.

Sometimes it is hard to distinguish the difference between an allergic reaction and an intolerance because they may have the some of the same symptoms.

An intolerance or sensitivity happens when your child's body is not able to digest certain food properly or that a certain food irritates your child's digestive tract. Signs of intolerance can be an upset stomach, burping, nausea, diarrhea, headaches, gas, nervousness, or irritability. While intolerances are uncomfortable, they do not affect the immune system, it is rarely dangerous, and the signs will go away when the food has passed through the body.

Even though Celiac Disease is classified as intolerance, it closely resembles an allergic disease of the gastrointestinal system. This condition is intolerance to all foods containing gluten. Children with this condition are at risk of having an anaphylaxis reaction, a situation where there is a rapid constriction of the airway, changing heart rhythms, internal intestinal problems, or external skin irritations.

Conclusions. Sometimes the symptoms of a food allergy may not be a food allergy, but signs of other allergic diseases of the gastrointestinal tract. Treatable gastrointestinal conditions include inflammatory bowel disease, Crohn's disease, motility disorder, Celiac disease, cyclic vomiting syndrome, and persistent diarrhea. Left untreated, allergic diseases can affect a child's growth.

Food allergies can be identified by testing while food intolerances will not show up on any test. Most children outgrow their allergies within a few years. However, children with more serious allergies, such as those related to peanuts or tree nuts, may never outgrow their reactions. The good news is that with a proper diagnosis and a treatment program from a pediatric gastroenterologist, you will know how to care for your child's food or other gastrointestinal allergies.

Timely, targeted, complete diagnosis prevents serious complications of these diseases.

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